

Supplementary Table S1. Primer sequences

Gene Name	Gene symbol	Forward	Reverse
Fatty acid synthase	<i>FASN</i>	AAGGACCTGTCTAGGTTTGATGC	TGGCTTCATAGGTGACTTCCA
Fatty acid elongase 6	<i>ELOVL6</i>	AGCAGTCAGTTTGTGACCAGG	ATCTCCTAGTTCGGGTGCTTT
Stearoyl-CoA desaturase	<i>SCD1</i>	TCTAGCTCCTATAACCACCACCA	TCGTCTCCAACCTTATCTCCTCC
Diacylglycerol O-acyltransferase 1	<i>DGAT1</i>	TATTGCGGCCAATGTCTTTGC	CACTGGAGTGATAGACTCAACCA
Diacylglycerol O-acyltransferase 2	<i>DGAT2</i>	ATTGCTGGCTCATCGCTGT	GGGAAAGTAGTCTCGAAAGTAGC
Acetyl-CoA carboxylase alpha	<i>ACC</i>	ATGTCTGGCTTGACCTAGTA	CCCCAAAGCGAGTAACAAATTCT
ATP citrate lyase	<i>ACLY</i>	TCGGCCAAGGCAATTCAGAG	CGAGCATACTTGAACCGATTCT
RNA, 18S ribosomal	<i>18S</i>	CCTCCAATGGATCCTCGTTA	AAACGGCTACCACATCCAAG

Supplementary Table S2. Fatty acids (g/day) intake from food frequency questionnaires.

	No MASLD (N = 26)	MASL (N = 33)	MASH (N = 32)	<i>p</i>
SFAs	63.67 ± 40.75	62.89 ± 57.90	72.28 ± 61.62	0.685
<i>C14:0</i>	2.54 ± 2.67	2.13 ± 2.98	2.75 ± 3.37	0.778
<i>C16:0</i>	22.19 ± 18.86	20.85 ± 20.98	24.49 ± 25.29	0.687
<i>C18:0</i>	8.38 ± 7.19	7.49 ± 7.52	9.08 ± 9.37	0.596
MUFAs	88.61 ± 57.57	81.08 ± 56.13	97.34 ± 81.75	0.618
<i>C18:1</i>	57.57 ± 42.35	50.75 ± 35.60	64.24 ± 57.53	0.801
PUFAs	38.85 ± 27.41	36.51 ± 27.02	41.34 ± 34.41	0.675
<i>C18:2n6</i>	20.89 ± 18.76	23.11 ± 19.59	25.32 ± 29.34	0.896
<i>C18:3n3</i>	1.48 ± 1.58	1.59 ± 1.82	1.56 ± 1.62	0.849
<i>C20:4n6</i>	0.19 ± 0.18	0.11 ± 0.11	0.12 ± 0.10	0.243
<i>C20:5n3</i>	0.36 ± 0.28	0.23 ± 0.21	0.31 ± 0.34	0.266
<i>C22:6n3</i>	0.69 ± 0.47	0.45 ± 0.43	0.58 ± 0.63	0.181

Values are expressed as g/day (mean ± standard deviation). All variables were assessed for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test. Statistical differences were calculated using Kruskal-Wallis test considering $p < 0.05$ significant. MASH, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis; MASL, metabolic dysfunction-associated liver; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; MUFAs, monounsaturated fatty acids; PUFAs, polyunsaturated fatty acids; SFA, saturated fatty acids.

Supplementary Table S3. Fatty acid composition in liver tissue samples in $\mu\text{mol/g}$ tissue.

	No MASLD (N = 26)	MASL (N = 33)	MASH (N = 32)	p
SFAs	56.909 $\pm$ 19.263 ^a	101.833 $\pm$ 50.647 ^b	182.259 $\pm$ 91.307 ^c	< 0.001
OCFAs	0.955 $\pm$ 0.302 ^a	1.672 $\pm$ 0.911 ^b	2.723 $\pm$ 1.349 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C13:0</i>	0.017 $\pm$ 0.008 ^a	0.032 $\pm$ 0.022 ^a	0.053 $\pm$ 0.034 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C15:0</i>	0.379 $\pm$ 0.145 ^a	0.684 $\pm$ 0.440 ^b	1.158 $\pm$ 0.642 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C17:0</i>	0.429 $\pm$ 0.139 ^a	0.825 $\pm$ 0.438 ^b	1.354 $\pm$ 0.684 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C19:0</i>	0.024 $\pm$ 0.010 ^a	0.029 $\pm$ 0.016 ^a	0.044 $\pm$ 0.020 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C21:0</i>	0.015 $\pm$ 0.007 ^a	0.021 $\pm$ 0.007 ^b	0.029 $\pm$ 0.016 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C23:0</i>	0.072 $\pm$ 0.033	0.063 $\pm$ 0.019	0.061 $\pm$ 0.023	0.399
ECFAs	55.649 $\pm$ 18.905 ^a	99.562 $\pm$ 49.431 ^b	178.421 $\pm$ 89.349 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C10:0</i>	0.037 $\pm$ 0.019 ^a	0.064 $\pm$ 0.032 ^b	0.104 $\pm$ 0.088 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C12:0</i>	0.301 $\pm$ 0.197 ^a	0.628 $\pm$ 0.569 ^b	1.199 $\pm$ 0.914 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C14:0</i>	2.196 $\pm$ 1.672 ^a	5.316 $\pm$ 3.784 ^b	11.173 $\pm$ 7.518 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C16:0</i>	37.167 $\pm$ 15.177 ^a	72.418 $\pm$ 40.219 ^b	135.905 $\pm$ 70.274 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C18:0</i>	15.424 $\pm$ 3.698 ^a	20.567 $\pm$ 5.551 ^b	29.409 $\pm$ 11.682 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C20:0</i>	0.109 $\pm$ 0.042 ^a	0.166 $\pm$ 0.070 ^b	0.249 $\pm$ 0.127 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C22:0</i>	0.198 $\pm$ 0.071	0.195 $\pm$ 0.048	0.194 $\pm$ 0.055	0.972
<i>C24:0</i>	0.220 $\pm$ 0.089	0.215 $\pm$ 0.055	0.203 $\pm$ 0.067	0.613
MUFAs	46.766 $\pm$ 24.444 ^a	104.162 $\pm$ 69.920 ^b	197.299 $\pm$ 98.991 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C14:1n9</i>	0.045 $\pm$ 0.030 ^a	0.065 $\pm$ 0.046 ^{a,b}	0.097 $\pm$ 0.067 ^b	0.001
<i>C14:1n11</i>	0.127 $\pm$ 0.136 ^a	0.259 $\pm$ 0.218 ^b	0.607 $\pm$ 0.558 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C16:1</i>	5.473 $\pm$ 3.817 ^a	10.841 $\pm$ 7.132 ^b	20.822 $\pm$ 11.840 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C17:1</i>	0.161 $\pm$ 0.120 ^a	0.395 $\pm$ 0.335 ^b	0.749 $\pm$ 0.459 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C18:1</i>	40.545 $\pm$ 20.739 ^a	91.848 $\pm$ 62.274 ^b	173.799 $\pm$ 87.752 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C19:1</i>	0.019 $\pm$ 0.010 ^a	0.043 $\pm$ 0.032 ^b	0.068 $\pm$ 0.038 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C20:1</i>	0.230 $\pm$ 0.111 ^a	0.557 $\pm$ 0.426 ^b	0.962 $\pm$ 0.501 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C22:1</i>	0.030 $\pm$ 0.022 ^a	0.034 $\pm$ 0.016 ^a	0.069 $\pm$ 0.052 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C24:1</i>	0.132 $\pm$ 0.061	0.116 $\pm$ 0.036	0.114 $\pm$ 0.041	0.275
n-6 PUFAs	37.354 $\pm$ 9.068 ^a	60.512 $\pm$ 35.339 ^b	85.405 $\pm$ 37.350 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C16:2n6</i>	0.049 $\pm$ 0.028 ^a	0.153 $\pm$ 0.170 ^b	0.259 $\pm$ 0.163 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C18:2n6</i>	25.758 $\pm$ 7.239 ^a	48.869 $\pm$ 35.052 ^b	74.596 $\pm$ 36.829 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C20:2n6</i>	0.247 $\pm$ 0.095 ^a	0.406 $\pm$ 0.291 ^b	0.499 $\pm$ 0.306 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C20:3n6</i>	1.852 $\pm$ 0.629	1.978 $\pm$ 0.384	1.821 $\pm$ 0.725	0.536
<i>C20:4n6</i>	8.922 $\pm$ 2.727	8.667 $\pm$ 2.006	7.569 $\pm$ 2.239	0.161
<i>C22:4n6</i>	0.247 $\pm$ 0.095 ^a	0.406 $\pm$ 0.295 ^b	0.499 $\pm$ 0.306 ^b	0.616
<i>C22:5n6</i>	0.188 $\pm$ 0.126 ^{a,b}	0.163 $\pm$ 0.078 ^a	0.128 $\pm$ 0.075 ^b	0.024
n-3 PUFAs	3.917 $\pm$ 1.574	4.131 $\pm$ 1.029	4.432 $\pm$ 1.481	0.149
<i>C18:3n3</i>	0.269 $\pm$ 0.167 ^a	0.595 $\pm$ 0.496 ^b	0.963 $\pm$ 0.591 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C20:4n3</i>	0.041 $\pm$ 0.026	0.047 $\pm$ 0.024	0.042 $\pm$ 0.029	0.457
<i>C20:5n3</i>	0.315 $\pm$ 0.243	0.326 $\pm$ 0.134	0.409 $\pm$ 0.249	0.085
<i>C22:5n3</i>	0.307 $\pm$ 0.163	0.339 $\pm$ 0.159	0.316 $\pm$ 0.171	0.735
<i>C22:6n3</i>	2.985 $\pm$ 1.212	2.825 $\pm$ 0.705	2.716 $\pm$ 1.106	0.345
n-6/n-3 PUFAs	11.124 $\pm$ 6.174 ^a	14.788 $\pm$ 6.059 ^b	20.239 $\pm$ 8.436 ^c	< 0.001

Values are expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation. All variables were assessed for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test. Statistical differences were calculated using ANOVA test in those parameters with normal distribution (i.e., C13:0, C19:0, C22:0, C24:1, C20:3n6, C22:4n6, and C22:5n3) and Kruskal-Wallis tests for parameters without normal distribution considering $p < 0.05$ significant. Bonferroni post hoc analysis was performed for the intergroup differences test in those parameters with a significant p . ECFAs, even chain fatty acids; MASH, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis; MASL, metabolic dysfunction-associated liver; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; MUFAs, monounsaturated fatty acids; OCFAs, odd chain fatty acids; PUFAs, polyunsaturated fatty acids; SFA, saturated fatty acids. C9:0, C11:0; C25:0, C26:0 and C12:1 determination below limit of detection.

Supplementary Table S4. Fatty acid composition in liver samples in percentage to total fatty acids.

	No MASLD (N=26)	MASL (N=33)	MASH (N=32)	<i>p</i>
SFAs	37.611 ± 2.336	36.364 ± 2.678	36.695 ± 3.505	0.271
OCFAs	0.642 ± 0.104 ^a	0.603 ± 0.101 ^{a,b}	0.557 ± 0.093 ^b	0.018
<i>C15:0</i>	0.228 ± 0.047	0.222 ± 0.050	0.215 ± 0.048	0.622
<i>C17:0</i>	0.295 ± 0.058	0.305 ± 0.053	0.285 ± 0.056	0.362
ECFAs	36.770 ± 2.378	35.546 ± 2.677	35.925 ± 3.492	0.337
<i>C12:0</i>	0.151 ± 0.081	0.160 ± 0.067	0.178 ± 0.074	0.189
<i>C14:0</i>	1.173 ± 0.550 ^a	1.542 ± 0.440 ^b	1.864 ± 0.591 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C16:0</i>	23.454 ± 2.563 ^a	24.824 ± 2.418 ^a	26.789 ± 3.013 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C18:0</i>	11.522 ± 2.504 ^a	8.687 ± 1.856 ^b	6.896 ± 1.284 ^c	< 0.001
MUFAs	30.928 ± 6.533 ^a	37.766 ± 3.795 ^b	42.187 ± 3.481 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C16:1</i>	3.197 ± 1.258	3.565 ± 0.948	3.993 ± 1.279	0.066
<i>C18:1</i>	27.206 ± 5.673 ^a	33.641 ± 3.419 ^b	37.613 ± 3.340 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C20:1</i>	0.174 ± 0.042 ^a	0.225 ± 0.065 ^b	0.233 ± 0.048 ^b	0.001
n-6 PUFAs	27.972 ± 4.542 ^a	23.729 ± 3.499 ^b	19.759 ± 4.365 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C18:2n6</i>	18.434 ± 2.423	17.952 ± 2.929	16.583 ± 3.937	0.073
<i>C20:2n6</i>	0.199 ± 0.076 ^a	0.173 ± 0.054 ^a	0.127 ± 0.053 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C20:3n6</i>	1.497 ± 0.457 ^a	0.963 ± 0.371 ^b	0.505 ± 0.229 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C20:4n6</i>	7.427 ± 2.597 ^a	4.369 ± 2.135 ^b	2.379 ± 1.435 ^c	< 0.001
n-3 PUFAs	3.488 ± 1.637 ^a	2.143 ± 1.093 ^b	1.360 ± 0.869 ^c	< 0.001
<i>C18:3n3</i>	0.179 ± 0.066	0.214 ± 0.084	0.205 ± 0.075	0.203
<i>C20:5n3</i>	0.257 ± 0.197 ^a	0.165 ± 0.116 ^a	0.127 ± 0.142 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C22:5n3</i>	0.274 ± 0.131 ^a	0.178 ± 0.097 ^a	0.102 ± 0.076 ^b	< 0.001
<i>C22:6n3</i>	2.745 ± 1.365 ^a	1.563 ± 0.889 ^b	0.918 ± 0.678 ^c	< 0.001
n-6/n-3 PUFAs	9.972 ± 5.654 ^a	13.283 ± 5.536 ^b	18.319 ± 7.785 ^c	< 0.001

Values are expressed as percentage to total fatty acids (mean ± standard deviation). All variables were assessed for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test. Statistical differences were calculated using ANOVA test in those parameters with normal distribution (i.e., *C15:0*, *C17:0*, *C18:0*, MUFAs, *C18:1*, n-6 PUFAs, *C18:2n6*, *C20:2n6*, and *C20:3n6*) and Kruskal-Wallis tests for parameters without normal distribution considering $p < 0.05$ significant. Bonferroni post hoc analysis was performed for the intergroup differences test in those parameters with a significant p . ECFAs, even chain fatty acids; MASH, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis; MASL, metabolic dysfunction-associated liver; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; MUFAs, monounsaturated fatty acids; OCFAs, odd chain fatty acids; PUFAs, polyunsaturated fatty acids; SFA, saturated fatty acids. *C9:0*, *C11:0*; *C25:0*, *C26:0* and *C12:1* determination below limit of detection. Table shows only those fatty acids representing at least a 0.1% of total fatty acids.

Supplementary Table S5. Fatty acid composition in serum samples as $\mu\text{mol/L}$.

	No MASLD (N=26)	MASL (N=33)	MASH (N=32)	P
SFAs	4027.793 $\pm$ 1430.109	4326.874 $\pm$ 1273.083	4030.707 $\pm$ 1109.746	0.434
OCFAs	86.964 $\pm$ 20.157	95.899 $\pm$ 27.113	86.262 $\pm$ 23.128	0.229
<i>C13:0</i>	2.145 $\pm$ 1.154	2.12 $\pm$ 0.896	2.127 $\pm$ 1.018	0.774
<i>C15:0</i>	40.309 $\pm$ 11.842	44.174 $\pm$ 15.097	39.718 $\pm$ 15.869	0.441
<i>C17:0</i>	29.537 $\pm$ 1.964	33.466 $\pm$ 10.262	30.354 $\pm$ 7.855	0.204
<i>C19:0</i>	1.964 $\pm$ 2.610	2.051 $\pm$ 2.926	2.020 $\pm$ 1.001	0.949
<i>C21:0</i>	2.610 $\pm$ 1.351	2.926 $\pm$ 1.664	2.269 $\pm$ 1.243	0.247
<i>C23:0</i>	7.328 $\pm$ 2.787	7.687 $\pm$ 2.447	6.640 $\pm$ 2.197	0.150
<i>C25:0</i>	3.327 $\pm$ 1.568	4.088 $\pm$ 3.118	3.394 $\pm$ 1.589	0.742
ECFAs	3940.829 $\pm$ 1414.022	4230.975 $\pm$ 1253.281	3944.443 $\pm$ 1093.397	0.419
<i>C10:0</i>	33.577 $\pm$ 65.699	71.954 $\pm$ 196.965	20.423 $\pm$ 40.480	0.132
<i>C12:0</i>	61.865 $\pm$ 93.556	53.243 $\pm$ 57.994	27.734 $\pm$ 25.702	0.481
<i>C14:0</i>	188.542 $\pm$ 139.388	183.764 $\pm$ 113.445	142.658 $\pm$ 61.792	0.567
<i>C16:0</i>	2754.682 $\pm$ 1107.862	2918.397 $\pm$ 833.569	2843.399 $\pm$ 788.277	0.260
<i>C18:0</i>	842.648 $\pm$ 223.815	946.759 $\pm$ 217.532	857.708 $\pm$ 260.302	0.203
<i>C20:0</i>	17.114 $\pm$ 11.246 ^a	19.063 $\pm$ 10.197 ^b	14.298 $\pm$ 5.004 ^{a,b}	0.017
<i>C22:0</i>	27.224 $\pm$ 12.155	29.057 $\pm$ 9.461	24.115 $\pm$ 6.818	0.100
<i>C24:0</i>	23.259 $\pm$ 7.960 ^{a,b}	26.111 $\pm$ 7.352 ^a	21.299 $\pm$ 7.067 ^b	0.024
<i>C26:0</i>	1.213 $\pm$ 0.608	1.412 $\pm$ 0.553	1.233 $\pm$ 0.541	0.202
MUFAs	3597.336 $\pm$ 1355.190	3912.334 $\pm$ 1260.646	3568.129 $\pm$ 927.445	0.360
<i>C14:1n9</i>	8.207 $\pm$ 6.175	8.392 $\pm$ 5.093	6.732 $\pm$ 4.283	0.343
<i>C14:1n11</i>	7.121 $\pm$ 7.947	6.441 $\pm$ 5.991	4.651 $\pm$ 3.921	0.443
<i>C16:1</i>	447.922 $\pm$ 256.603	422.778 $\pm$ 142.917	417.099 $\pm$ 180.177	0.745
<i>C17:1</i>	12.126 $\pm$ 7.049	12.550 $\pm$ 4.246	12.446 $\pm$ 5.151	0.532
<i>C18:1</i>	3077.985 $\pm$ 1121.905	3417.406 $\pm$ 1160.388	3081.106 $\pm$ 778.690	0.350
<i>C19:1</i>	1.325 $\pm$ 0.784	1.777 $\pm$ 1.010	1.271 $\pm$ 0.414	0.114
<i>C20:1</i>	18.142 $\pm$ 17.188	22.112 $\pm$ 18.173	14.520 $\pm$ 7.756	0.391
<i>C22:1</i>	6.868 $\pm$ 16.516	4.266 $\pm$ 6.307	13.984 $\pm$ 62.971	0.861
<i>C24:1</i>	17.699 $\pm$ 6.886	16.669 $\pm$ 7.477	16.400 $\pm$ 5.582	0.770
n-6 PUFAs	4081.767 $\pm$ 1014.256	4396.010 $\pm$ 1078.726	3908.501 $\pm$ 1084.302	0.155
<i>C16:2n6</i>	1.941 $\pm$ 1.285	2.210 $\pm$ 1.642	2.088 $\pm$ 1.601	0.479
<i>C18:2n6</i>	3235.260 $\pm$ 892.047	3484.715 $\pm$ 939.944	3080.273 $\pm$ 918.934	0.219
<i>C20:2n6</i>	16.514 $\pm$ 7.887 ^{a,b}	20.708 $\pm$ 9.912 ^a	16.055 $\pm$ 10.077 ^b	0.037
<i>C20:3n6</i>	174.810 $\pm$ 89.439	190.898 $\pm$ 72.909	162.949 $\pm$ 76.826	0.187
<i>C20:4n6</i>	629.829 $\pm$ 162.408	671.232 $\pm$ 213.598	623.965 $\pm$ 170.721	0.561
<i>C22:4n6</i>	15.390 $\pm$ 7.655	17.876 $\pm$ 8.679	15.41 $\pm$ 7.596	0.411
<i>C22:5n6</i>	8.0223 $\pm$ 5.015	8.371 $\pm$ 4.560	7.759 $\pm$ 4.816	0.581
n-3 PUFAs	201.803 $\pm$ 70.337	255.023 $\pm$ 90.893	247.662 $\pm$ 95.131	0.077
<i>C18:3n3</i>	42.754 $\pm$ 19.071	47.326 $\pm$ 21.171	43.452 $\pm$ 19.853	0.598
<i>C20:4n3</i>	5.104 $\pm$ 2.179 ^{a,b}	6.992 $\pm$ 3.879 ^a	4.588 $\pm$ 3.333 ^b	0.017
<i>C20:5n3</i>	31.399 $\pm$ 16.033	43.357 $\pm$ 21.839	47.472 $\pm$ 38.608	0.100
<i>C22:5n3</i>	17.715 $\pm$ 6.242 ^a	25.669 $\pm$ 10.792 ^b	22.994 $\pm$ 8.558 ^b	0.008
<i>C22:6n3</i>	104.831 $\pm$ 42.167	131.677 $\pm$ 50.393	129.156 $\pm$ 48.883	0.102
sn-6/sn-3 PUFAs	22.202 $\pm$ 9.951	19.043 $\pm$ 6.894	16.909 $\pm$ 4.534	0.078

Values are expressed as $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (mean $\pm$ standard deviation). All variables were assessed for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test. Statistical differences were calculated using ANOVA test in those parameters with normal distribution (i.e. OCFAs, C15:0, C17:0, C19:0, C18:0, C26:0, C24:1, C20:4n6, n-3 PUFAs, C22:5n3, C22:6n3) and Kruskal-Wallis tests for parameters without normal distribution considering $p < 0.05$ significant. Bonferroni post hoc analysis was performed for the intergroup differences test in those parameters with a significant p . ECFAs, even chain fatty acids; MASH, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis; MASL, metabolic dysfunction-associated liver; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; MUFAs, monounsaturated fatty acids; OCFAs, odd chain fatty acids; PUFAs, polyunsaturated fatty acids; SFA, saturated fatty acids. C9:0, C11:0 and C12:1 determination below limit of detection.

Supplementary Table S6. Fatty acid composition in percentage to total fatty acids in serum samples.

	No MASLD (N=26)	MASL (N=33)	MASH (N=32)	<i>p</i>
sSFAs	31.994 ± 2.389	31.8226 ± 1.736	32.655 ± 2.419	0.294
sOCFAs	0.727 ± 0.135	0.735 ± 0.142	0.718 ± 0.122	0.873
sC15:0	0.303 ± 0.071	0.302 ± 0.081	0.297 ± 0.100	0.959
sC17:0	0.249 ± 0.050	0.256 ± 0.048	0.253 ± 0.032	0.840
sECFAs	31.019 ± 2.318	30.858 ± 1.671	31.708 ± 2.405	0.434
sC12:0	0.124 ± 0.046	0.265 ± 0.226	0.170 ± 0.151	0.508
sC14:0	1.259 ± 0.796	1.123 ± 0.520	0.978 ± 0.257	0.720
sC16:0	21.169 ± 2.363 ^a	20.896 ± 1.417 ^a	22.383 ± 1.936 ^b	0.006
sC18:0	7.369 ± 0.922	7.642 ± 0.791	7.466 ± 1.076	0.559
sC20:0	0.164 ± 0.092	0.164 ± 0.062	0.139 ± 0.034	0.257
sC22:0	0.292 ± 0.117	0.281 ± 0.066	0.261 ± 0.075	0.399
sC24:0	0.274 ± 0.098	0.276 ± 0.074	0.247 ± 0.072	0.279
sMUFAs	30.083 ± 3.065	30.381 ± 2.969	30.760 ± 2.743	0.448
sC16:1	3.326 ± 0.896	3.008 ± 0.719	3.198 ± 0.796	0.344
sC18:1	26.097 ± 2.920	26.374 ± 2.403	26.898 ± 2.710	0.596
sC20:1	0.176 ± 0.199	0.181 ± 0.115	0.138 ± 0.053	0.536
sC24:1	0.209 ± 0.094	0.181 ± 0.092	0.193 ± 0.073	0.513
sn-6 PUFAs	35.971 ± 4.312	35.543 ± 3.498	34.192 ± 3.690	0.135
sC18:2n6	27.954 ± 4.116	27.683 ± 3.954	26.397 ± 3.651	0.398
sC20:2n6	0.153 ± 0.053	0.176 ± 0.599	0.143 ± 0.055	0.061
sC20:3n6	1.594 ± 0.417	1.629 ± 0.427	1.487 ± 0.461	0.308
sC20:4n6	6.019 ± 1.374	5.798 ± 1.658	5.919 ± 1.246	0.856
sC22:4n6	0.156 ± 0.049	0.163 ± 0.059	0.154 ± 0.051	0.879
sn-3 PUFAs	1.957 ± 0.533	2.250 ± 0.671	2.388 ± 0.745	0.184
sC18:3n3	0.361 ± 0.144	0.367 ± 0.144	0.365 ± 0.118	0.988
sC20:5n3	0.294 ± 0.141	0.371 ± 0.186	0.446 ± 0.351	0.097
sC22:5n3	0.185 ± 0.061	0.234 ± 0.073	0.234 ± 0.068	0.032
sC22:6n3	1.071 ± 0.356	1.222 ± 0.432	1.300 ± 0.390	0.199
sn-6/sn-3 PUFAs	20.303 ± 9.198 ^a	17.379 ± 6.358 ^{a,b}	15.399 ± 4.161 ^b	0.047

Values are expressed as percentage to total fatty acids (mean ± standard deviation). All variables were assessed for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test. Statistical differences were calculated using ANOVA test in those parameters with normal distribution (i.e., SFAs, C15:0, C17:0, C16:0, C18:0, C22:0, C16:1, C18:1, C24:1, C20:2n6, C20:4n6, C18:3n3, and C20:5n3) and Kruskal-Wallis tests for parameters without normal distribution considering $p < 0.05$ significant. Bonferroni post hoc analysis was performed for the intergroup differences test in those parameters with a significant p . ECFAs, even chain fatty acids; MASH, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis; MASL, metabolic dysfunction-associated liver; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; MUFAs, monounsaturated fatty acids; OCFAs, odd chain fatty acids; PUFAs, polyunsaturated fatty acids; SFA, saturated fatty acids. Table shows only those FAs representing at least a 0.1% of total FAs.

Supplementary Table S7. Correlations between serum FA levels and histopathological/biochemical parameters.

	sOCFAs	sECFAs	sMUFAs	n-6 sPUFAs	n-3 sPUFAs
<i>Histopathological diagnosis</i>	-0.035	0.069	0.073	-0.058	0.172
<i>SAF score</i>	-0.087	0.048	0.047	-0.040	0.083
<i>Steatosis</i>	-0.021	0.087	0.093	0.007	0.126
<i>Hepatocyte ballooning</i>	-0.094	0.045	0.036	-0.027	0.044
<i>Lobular inflammation</i>	-0.138	-0.025	-0.030	-0.133	0.024
<i>Fibrosis</i>	-0.045	-0.006	0.063	-0.082	0.047

Values are presented as Spearman correlation coefficient. SAF, steatosis, activity, and fibrosis; sECFAs, serum even chain fatty acids; sMUFAs, serum monounsaturated fatty acids; sOCFAs, serum odd chain fatty acids; sPUFAs, serum polyunsaturated fatty acids. **Denotes $p < 0.01$. *Denotes $p < 0.05$.

Supplementary Table S8. Correlations between hepatic FA ratios and gene expression levels of FA metabolism enzymes.

	C18:0/C16:0	C16:1/C16:0	C18:1/C18:0
<i>FASN</i>	-0.259*	0.166	0.229*
<i>ELOVL6</i>	-0.197	-0.075	0.252*
<i>SCD1</i>	-0.241*	0.086	0.213
<i>DGAT1</i>	-0.319**	-0.001	0.320**
<i>DGAT2</i>	-0.260*	0.017	0.313**
<i>ACC</i>	-0.156	-0.081	0.177
<i>ACLY</i>	-0.231*	-0.090	0.238*

Values are presented as Spearman correlation coefficient. *ACC*, acetyl-CoA carboxylase; *ACLY*, ATP citrate synthase; *DGAT1*, diacylglycerol acyltransferase-1; *DGAT2*, diacylglycerol acyltransferase-2; *ELOVL6*, fatty acid elongase 6; *FAS*, fatty acid synthase; *SCD1*, stearoyl-CoA desaturase-1. **Denotes $p < 0.01$. *Denotes $p < 0.05$.